

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDENTS AT ADEYEMI FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

AKINMUSIRE, ALIU PATRICK (Ph.D)

DEPARTMENT OF CURRICULUM AND INSTRUCTION
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, ONDO,
ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study was carried out on impact of social media on academic achievement of English Language students at Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria. the population of the study comprised, English Language students, the sample size of the study was Two hundred (200) respondents. A simple random sampling technique was used to select fifty (50) English Language students from each of the levels (100, 200, 300 and 400), respectively. The research instrument that was used to gather data was self-designed and developed by the researcher, titled “Impact of social media on academic achievement of English Language students at Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria”. It was fashioned on polar questions i.e Yes and No answers. The research instrument was validated by two experts in test and measurement, while its reliability was done through test retest method, at two weeks interval and 0.66 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data generated was analyzed using descriptive statistics (simple percentage, frequency counts). Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were made that social media could enhance students interest motivate and make them to be addictive to their studies premised on the conclusions, the researcher therefore made the following recommendations; students should be encourage to be making use of social media to enhance their academic performance. Students should have access to social media devices and so on.

Keywords: Impact, Social media, Academic, Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

Currently, the world is undergoing major transformations. The transformation is multi-dimensional, affecting the technological, economic, social, cultural, political and educational development of all human endeavours and activities in many nations, Nigeria, inclusive. One of such transformations is the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT), which social media devices such as internet, 2go, google sites etc are by products.

Modern Technology in communication has turned the entire world into a “Global village” thus, making global interaction possible. But as it is, technology like two sides of a coin, with both negative and positive effects. It helps people to be better informed, enlightened, and keeping abreast with world innovations and developments. Technology exposes mankind to a better way of doing things and convenient life. Social networking sites include; Twitter, Yahoo Messenger, Facebook Messenger, Blackberry Messenger (BBM), Whatsapp messenger, 2go messenger, Skype, Google Messenger. These

networking sites are used by most people to interact people in respect of the distance (Asemah, et al., 2012). The world has been transformed rapidly by the evolution of ICT. It has also resulted into the use of technology as the best medium to explore the wide area of knowledge. Today, globally, ICT occupies important position in teaching and learning.

The evolution of internet technology has led to its use as the best medium for communication. Whereby, two-third of the world's internet population visits social networking or blogging sites, thus serving as a communication and connection tool. Social networking sites (SNSs) are online Communities of internet users, who want to communicate with other users about areas of mutual interest, whether from a personal, business or academic perspective (William, et al., 2009). The millions of social networking sites have transformed the thought of global village into a reality whereby billions of people communicate through social networking sites. Numerous benefits have been obtained through distant communication through the use of social networking sites. Today, most youths and students possess Facebook accounts, My Space, Twitter Whatsapp and so on.

The reason while most of them are performing badly in school might not be far-fetched. While many minds might be quick to blame the poor quality of teachers, they might have to think even harder, if they have not heard of the Facebook frenzy Olubiyi (2012), noted that these days' students are so engrossed in the social media usage that they are almost 24 hours online. Even in classrooms and lecture theatres, it has been observed that some students are always busy ping, watsapping, 2going or Facebooking, while lectures are on. Times that ought be channeled towards serious learning, academic researches and innovating have been crushed by the passion for meeting ne friends online, and most times busy discussing trivial issues in some cases, engaging in internet frauds. Hence, most students' academic suffer setback as a result of distraction from social media. Obi et al., (2012) observed that the use of these sites also affects students' use of English and grammar. The students are used to short forms of writing words in their chat rooms; they forget and use the same in the classrooms. They use things like 4 in place of for, U in place of You, D in place of The and so on, and this could affect their class assessment.

Social networking sites although has been recognized as an important resource for education today, studies however shows that students use social networking sites such as Facebook for fun, to kill time, to meet existing friends or to make new ones rather than using for meaningful academic activities (Ellison, 2007). Although it has been noticed that students spends much time on participating in social networking activities, with many students blaming the various social networking sites for their steady decrease in grade point average (Kimberly, 2009), it also shows that only few students are aware of the academic and professional networking opportunities the sites offered.

Researches have identified and showed that most tertiary institutions students would prefer to use social media and spend many hours checking social media sites. Social networking is definitely affecting students' efficiencies, as well as, their grades levels.

On the other side, the negative influences of social media includes; distraction, lack or loss of interest in reading, laziness, internet crime, and examination malpractices to mention but a few result from students addiction to social media and it contributes immensely to the diminishing standard of education in Nigeria. On the other hand, the use of ICT tools has make teaching and learning processes more pleasurable. It is being used as instructional materials to enrich knowledge acquisition. Several researches have been carried out on the use of ICT in teaching and learning across all levels of educators in diverse forms, but much seem not to have been done on English Language. English Language occupies a key position in Nigeria. it is a language of communication among members of different ethnic groups. It is a language of business, financial and legal transactions. English Language is a language of communication at national assemblies and a major language of instruction in Nigerian schools at all levels. It is a discipline and a subject which a student must compulsorily pass to secure admission. It is against this background the study was carried out on impact of ICT on impact of social media on academic achievement of English Language students at Federal University of Education, , Ondo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The world today is a global market in which the internet is the most important sort of information. Since the advent of social media sites in the 1990s, it is assumed and believed in some quarters that the academic performance of students is facing a lot of positive and negative influences due to social media usage. Social media did make the world a smaller place, now we have more information, more knowledge, and have better opportunities to use it. Google has helped over 20 million students in their education using their tools. By spending so much time working with new technology, students develop more familiarity with computers and other electronic devices. With the increased focus on technology in education and business, this will help students build skills that will aid them throughout their lives. Talents got discovered faster, students who were

good at programming got their names easily, students who were good in music, got their videos out and shared leading them to dreams.

It is mainly used for connecting students with one another over the phone, which leads to less face-to-face interaction. Also, it can cause major stress and anxiety, cyber bullying, distraction and behaviour issues. The dwindling in academic performance of students have been attributed to social media usage while to some scholars they contend that social media usage has positive influence on academic performance of students. Thus, poses question that needs investigation. It was against this backdrop that motivated the researcher to conduct the study.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was on impact of social media on academic achievement of English Language students at Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. The specific purposes were to:

1. ascertain the extent to which addictiveness to social media usage could influence English Language students' academic performance in Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria
2. determine the extent to which the use of social media usage could influence English Language interests on their studies
3. examine if there is any significance gender difference in the students' usage of social media networking in Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. Can ICT utilization improve academic achievement of English Language students?
2. Will ICT utilization make English Language students to be addictive to their studies?
3. Does ICT motivate English Language students towards learning?
4. Can ICT utilization make students to cultivate self-study habit?

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will be of great importance to stakeholders in English Language in the following ways;

The result of the study will help the teachers of the school to know the influences that social media has on their students, thus enable them to enlighten and create awareness to the English Language students on the possible influence social media usage has on their academic achievement. The study is of significant to parents in the sense that they will know the possible effects these social media usage has on their children, so as to serve as watch-dog to their children on the usage of the social networking site.

The result of the study will enable the English Language students to be aware that, apart from the social benefits of using social networking sites, using the sites outside academic ill negatively affecting their academic achievement. It will provide relevant materials for students and other researchers undertaking similar research future and so on.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Social Media

Social media is the means the employ mobile and web based technology to create highly interactive platforms via which individuals and community share, co-create, discuss and modifies user-generated content (Kietzmannn, 2012). Social media is a phrase being tossed around a lot. It is a website that does not just give you information but interact with you while giving you information. It is a group of internet based application that allows the creation and exchange of users generated content. It is easy to confuse social media with social news because we often refer to members of the news as the media. Adding to it, that social news site is also social media site. Some media website includes:

Social Bookmarking: interact by tagging website and searching through website book marked by others (Blink list, simple).

Social News: interact by voting for articles and commenting on them (Digg, propello).

Social Networking: interact by adding friends, commenting on photo and profiles, sharing groups for discussions (Facebook, 2go, BB chat)

Social Photo and Video Sharing: interact by sharing photos or videos and commenting on the user submission. (Youtube and Fliki).

Wikis: Interact by adding articles and editing existing articles. (Wikipedia, wikia).

Social media refers to the means of interaction among people in which they create, share, exchange and comment among themselves in different networks. Andreas and Michael (2010) are of the opinion that social media is a group of internet based application that builds on the ideological foundation and allows the creation and exchange of users generated content. Social media has become one of the major channel of chatting through platforms such as 2go, BB chat, blogger and wikia. There has been an increase in the mobile social media which has created new opportunity for browsing. The internet usage effect of social media, in views of Nielsen (2012) is that, students continue to spend more time on the social media than any site. The total time spent on social media across mobile devices increased by 37%, 121 billion minutes in July 2012 compared to 88 billion minutes in July 2011.

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) classified social media into six different classes as follows:

1. Collaborative Project (Wikipedia)
2. Blogs and Micro blogs (Twitter)
3. Content Communities (Youtube)
4. Social Networking Site (Facebook; 2go; BB chat)
5. Virtual Game World (World of war craft)
6. Virtual Second World (Second life)

Technology includes the blog, picture sharing, music sharing, crowd sourcing, E-mail, instant messaging and voice over. These services could be integrated via social network aggregation platforms.

Usage of Social Media and Students' Academic Achievement

The social media engages students and have to be examined as entrepreneurs of understanding. The medium of internet is marketing with increase in its programs. The interactive character of online conditions has extended with social networking. Hooking up through social networking began as being a niche activity, though time it's a phenomenon. The web sites are employed in many ways like developing metropolitan areas, speaking, blogging etc. Additionally different institutions even nowadays are developing groups on several Websites (Saba Mehmood, 2013).

The improved usage of Websites has become a worldwide phenomenon for quite some time. What began out as being a hobby for several computer literate people has converted to a social norm and existence-style for individuals from around the globe (Nicole Ellison, 2007).Teens and teenagers have especially recognized these internet sites to be able to contact their peers, share information, reinvent their personas, and showcase their social lives Nicole Ellison,(2007).While using the increase of technology helpful for getting together with others along with the recognition on the internet, Internet sites are now being an activity that's done mainly on the web, with Websites Vaughn, Coyle (2008).

According to Khan (2009), social media users often time experience poor performance academically. Similarly, Englander, Terregrossa & Wang (2010) posit that social media is negatively associated with academic performance of student and is a lot more momentous than its advantages. Internet addiction consequently gave rise in internet usage within the last couple of decades. Nalwa & Anand (2003).recommended that addicted users prefer using internet setting back their personal and professional responsibilities which ultimately leads to poor academic performance. In the same vein, Karpinski (2009) pointed out that social media users devoted lesser time to their studies in comparison to nonusers did and subsequently had lower GPAs. Karpinski& Duberstein. (2009).Also mentioned that among various unique distractions of every single generation, Social media remains a major distraction of current generation.

3. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. This design was considered, because it enables the researcher to generate through the standardized collection procedures based on highly structured research instrument(s), well defined study concepts and related variables. The population of the study comprised English Language students at Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Two hundred respondents were used as the sample size for the study drew through a simple random sampling technique, fifty (50) respondents were selected from 100, 200, 300 and 400 levels, respectively.

A self-developed questionnaire by the researcher titles, “impact of social media on academic achievement of English Language students at Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria”. The research used to get the desired information from the students. Instrument was validated by an expert in test and measurement. The reliability of the instrument was done through, test retest method and 0.66 coefficient reliability was obtained. This was done at an interval of two weeks. This made the instrument to be found to have reliability value. Hence, used for the study. Descriptive statistics (frequency counts and simple percentages) were used to analyzed data generated on the research questions.

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Result

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: Can ICT Utilization improve academic performance of English Language students?

Table 1: Showing frequency counts and simple percentages on can ICT Utilization improve academic performance of English Language students.

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%
1	ICT utilization improve my acquisition of knowledge	181	90.5	19	9.5
2	ICT utilization hinders acquisition of knowledge	28	14	172	86
3	Using ICT enhance the rate at which I understand topics taught with the use of ICT, utilization	156	78	44	22
4	I don't understand topics taught with the use of ICT utilization	50	25	150	75
5	ICT utilization makes me to be always studying	140	70	60	30
6	I rarely study, using ICT	70	35	130	65

Table 1 presents the findings on research question one. On item (1), 181 (90.5%) and 19(9.5%), among the respondents responded Yes and No. On item (2) 28 (14%) and 176(86%) responses were got for Yes and No, respectively. On item (3), 156 (78%) and 44 (22%) responses were obtained for Yes and No, respectively. On item (4), 50 (25%) and 150 (75%) among the respondents responded Yes or No. on item (5), 140 (70%) and 60 (30%) of the responses were obtained for Yes and No, respectively. Finally, on item (6), 70 (35%) and 130 (65%) of the respondents responded Yes and No.

Research Question Two: Will ICT Utilization make English Language students, addictive to their studies?

Table 2: Showing frequency counts and simple percentages on Will ICT Utilization make English Language students, addictive to their studies.

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%
7	ICT utilization frequently make me to read	132	66	68	34
8	I seldomly read my book, using ICT	128	64	72	36
9	ICT utilization always encourage me to search for a knowledge	141	70.5	59	29.5
10	I do not use ICT regularly to search for new knowledge	40	20	160	80
11	I can't do without using ICT in a day for study	111	55.5	89	44.5
12	Using ICT often makes me to like studying	26	13	174	87

Table 2 shows the result on research question two. On item (7), 132 (66%) and 68 (34) among the respondents responded Yes and No. on item (8), 128 (64%) and 72 (36%) maintained) Yes and No. On Item (9), 141 (70.5) and 59 (29.5%) responded Yes or No, respectively. On item (10), 40 (20%) and 160 (80%) responses were obtained for Yes and No. On item (11), 111 (55.5%) and 89 (44.5%) also were obtained for Yes and No. Finally, on item (12), 26 (13%) and 174 (87%) were got for Yes and No.

Research Question Three: Does ICT motivate English Language students towards reading?

Table 3: Showing frequency counts and simple percentages on Does ICT motivate English Language students towards reading.

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%
13	I am always happy to use ICT for reading	127	63.5	73	36.5
14	ICT usage does not motivate me to read	16	8	184	92
15	ICT often create my mind towards reading	159	79.5	41	20.5
16	ICT makes reading very boring to me	10	5	190	95

Table three presents result on research question three. On item 13, 14, 15 and 16, the following responses were suggested; 127 (63.5%) and 73 (36.5%); 16 (8%) and 184 (92%); 159 (79.5%) and 41 (20.5%) and 10 (5%) and 190 (95%) responses were obtained for Yes and No.

Research Question Four: Can ICT utilization make English Language students to cultivate self-study habit?

Table 4: Showing frequency counts and simple percentages on Can ICT utilization make English Language students to cultivate self-study habit.

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%
17	Without teacher, ICT enable me to do personal study	171	85.5	29	14.5
18	ICT, makes personal study impossible	189	94.5	11	5.5
19	At any place, I can do study using ICT	160	80	40	20
20	ICT, restricted my studying habit	159	79.5	41	20.5
21	ICT don't enable me to do more of my study without teacher	79	39.5	121	60.5
22	Without teacher, I can't use ICT to study	169	84.5	31	15.5

Table four shows the result on research question five. On item 23, 24 and 25 the following responses were obtained Yes or No, respectively; 171 (85.5%) and 29 (14.5%); 189 (94.5%) and 11 (5.5%) and 160 (80%) and 40 (20%). Furthermore, on item 26, 27 and 28; 159 (79%) and 41 (20.5%); 79 (39.5%) and 121 (60.5%) and 169 (84.5%) and 31 (15.5%) were obtained, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The findings on research question one showed that social media utilization could improve academic performance of students. The result align with the view of Oyekan (2000), that ICT utilization by students, would make them to current better and higher performance in their academic.

On research question two, finding indicated that social media utilization could make students to be addictive to their studies. The findings is in consonance with Olubiyi (2012), who maintained that students have obsessive attitude to ICT use.

The findings on research question three revealed that ICT usage could motivate students towards learning. The result was corroborated by Maisaman, Adikwe, Victoria, Ogwuche, Ikwoche and Iriway (2018), social media has a veritable tool that could be used to enhance quality of education in various ways by increasing learners motivation and engagement with their learning.

Finally, the findings on research question four indicated that through the social media usage students could develop or cultivate a self-study habit. This agrees with the opinion of Adeyinka and Toyonbo (2007) that social media are transformational tools which when used appropriately could promote the shift to a learner-centered learning approach.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion were made that social media utilization could centres students' interest in their studies, students could achieve better academic performance, self-study habit could be developed and that students are motivated to learn.

6. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations, therefore were made;

1. Students should be advised to use social media for the purpose of academic
2. Students should be advised and encouraged to be making judicious use of social media
3. Students should have access to social media, especially ICT devices like web, internet etc
4. ICT should be made available at secondary schools in Nigeria
5. Students should be taught on how to use social media
6. Students should also be enlightened on the negative effects of social media to their studies and so on.

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